

Effect of phosphorus fertilizer on phosphorus transformation in rice soils

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We studied the transformation of added P in rice soils in a pot experiment using different P fertilizers. Black soil (8 kg available P/ha, 12.5 ppm Al-P, 3 ppm Fe-P, 103 ppm Ca-P) and alluvial soil (10 kg available P/ha, 21 ppm Al-P, 32 ppm Fe-P, 19 ppm Ca-P) were used. IR20 was the test variety. Ninety kg P/ha was applied in various forms (see table). Soil was sampled at tillering, panicle initiation, and harvest, and subjected to P fractionation using the Chang and Jackson procedure.

For black soil, Ca-P transformation was highest at all stages followed by that of Al-P and Fe-P. Fe-P transformation was dominant in alluvial soil, followed by that of Ca-P and Al-P (see table). In black soil, Al-P increased with growth stage. The other fractions increased up to panicle initiation. In alluvial soil, all the three P fractions increased to panicle initiation, then decreased to harvest. In diammonium phosphate-treated pots, Al-P was highest followed by that in pots with single superphosphate and monoammonium phosphate. In rock phosphate-treated pots, Fe-P and Ca-P were maximum (see table). □

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Fertilizer	Black soil			Alluvial soil		
	T	PI	H	T	PI	H
	<i>Aluminum-P</i>					
Diammonium phosphate	39	74	100	34	41	30
Monoammonium phosphate	43	58	64	35	45	43
Single superphosphate	40	45	101	28	45	45
Rock phosphate	33	65	50	34	43	41
Control	25	62	56	26	46	25
Mean	36	71	74	31	44	37
	<i>Iron-P</i>					
Diammonium phosphate	20	20	18	108	116	125
Monoammonium phosphate	30	20	45	88	125	125
Single superphosphate	20	45	15	100	114	100
Rock phosphate	20	60	15	100	161	116
Control	11	40	9	81	136	93
Mean	20	37	18	96	130	112
	<i>Calcium-P</i>					
Diammonium phosphate	188	250	218	98	93	88
Monoammonium phosphate	184	234	218	93	108	90
Single superphosphate	218	250	188	108	110	113
Rock phosphate	254	188	218	108	175	80
Control	182	232	160	90	120	71
Mean	205	231	200	99	121	88

Source of fertilizer	<i>Al-P</i>			<i>Fe-P</i>			<i>Ca-P</i>		
	F	SE	CD.	F	SE	CD.	F	SE	CD.
Soil	**	0.67	1.37	**	0.86	1.76	**	1.00	2.05
Stages	**	0.43	0.88	**	0.55	1.12	**	0.63	1.23
Sources and soils	**	0.52	1.06	**	0.67	1.37	**	0.77	1.57
Sources × stage	**	0.95	1.94	**	1.50	3.07	**	1.41	2.88
Stages × soil	**	1.17	2.39	**	1.22	2.50	**	1.72	3.52
	**	0.74	1.51	**	0.95	1.94	**	1.09	2.23

* T = tillering, PI = panicle initiation, H = harvest.

Response of rice cultivars to phosphorus

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Application of P as well as N has become necessary to maximize rice yields. Rice varieties differ in their ability to utilize soil and fertilizer P. We studied in 1983 the response of lowland rabi (Dec to Apr) rice to applied P on a soil with 14.7 kg available P/ha. Soil was clayey with pH 7.75, E.C. 0.62 dS/m, 0.77% organic carbon, and 390.2 kg available K/ha. The experiment was in a split-plot design with 6 rice varieties (IR50, BPT1235, MTU6783, MTU6910, MTU8922, and

Grain and straw yields of 6 rice varieties treated with 5 levels of P at Marutem, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)						Straw yield (t/ha)						Duration (d)
	0 P	17.5 kg P	26.2 kg P	35.0 kg P	43.7 kg P	Mean	0 P	17.5 kg P	26.2 kg P	35.0 kg P	43.7 kg P	Mean	
IR50	5.2	5.2	5.2	5.6	5.2	5.3	4.3	4.4	4.4	4.8	4.6	4.5	104
BPT1235	4.1	4.8	4.9	4.6	4.7	4.6	4.8	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.3	5.1	117
MTU6783	4.4	4.6	4.6	5.0	5.0	4.7	4.4	4.5	4.7	4.8	4.1	4.6	109
MTU6910	3.8	3.4	4.1	3.9	4.6	3.9	4.8	5.6	5.8	5.7	5.6	5.5	126
MTU8922	4.4	4.7	5.1	4.8	5.1	4.8	3.8	4.0	3.8	4.2	4.4	4.1	114
MTU2099	4.7	4.7	4.9	5.2	4.8	4.9	4.0	3.7	3.6	4.0	4.3	3.9	122

	F test	SEM	CD	F test	SEM	CD
P levels	S*	-	0.14	S*	-	0.07
Varieties	S*	-	0.18	S*	-	0.13
<i>Interactions</i>						
P level X Variety	S*	-	0.37	S*	-	0.26
Variety X P level	S*	-	0.39	S*	-	0.28
CV%			5.24			3.97

S* : Significant at 0.05 level.